

DISINFORMATION IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY: PROBLEMS AND CAUSES

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This article explores the factors that increase the risks of misinformation and disinformation; the reasons why the recipient of information is misled by the source of information. The quality of information may not be high enough to be trusted, but sufficient to be taken into account or disseminated, leading to an increase in rumours. An increase in the value of unverified information with a decrease in its quality leads to an increase in the risk of misinformation and disinformation.

ДЕЗИНФОРМАЦИИ В ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПРИЧИНЫ

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, экономика внимания, дезинформация, слухи

В данной статье исследуются факторы, увеличивающие риски дезинформации; причины введения в заблуждение получателя информации источником информации. Качество информации может быть недостаточно высоким, чтобы ей доверять, однако достаточным, чтобы принимать во внимание или распространять, что приводит к росту слухов. Увеличение ценности непроверенной информации при снижении ее качества приводит к увеличению риска дезинформации.

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA DEZINFORMATSIYANING TIZIMLI JIHATLARI

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, e'tibor iqtisodiyoti, dezinformatsiya, mish-mishlar

Ushbu maqola dezinformatsiya xavfini oshiradigan omillarni ko'rib chiqadi; axborot manbasi tomonidan ma'lumot oluvchini chalg'itish sabablari. Axborot sifati ishonchli bo'lishi mumkin emas, balki hisobga olinadigan yoki tarqatiladigan darajada yuqori bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa mish-mishlarning ko'payishiga olib keladi. Axborot sifatining pasayishi dezinformatsiya xavfining oshishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

The specific characteristic of the digital economy is that:

«as automation takes hold, it becomes obvious that information is the crucial commodity, and that solid products are merely incidental to information movement» [1],

«the main extracted and processed resource is data» [2].

M. Goldhaber drew attention to the consequences of the growth of information, noting that with the abundance of information and its sources in the digital world, the probability of paying attention to any particular part of it becomes less and less. This is evidence of limited attention [3].

The attention deficit, along with the processes of redistribution of advertising budgets, which entail the reduction of journalists' staff in traditional media, leads to an increase in the share of unverified information, hence rumours, as well as an increased risk of misinformation.

Factors affecting the risks of misinformation and disinformation

The factors influencing the risks of misinformation are the following:

at the level of information - on the one hand dissemination of information of low quality, for example, rumours causing emotional reactions, on the other hand insufficient influence of information quality on its value for the or the audience;

at the level of communication participants - on the one hand attention deficit that prevents checking the quality of information, on the other hand curiosity and ego of information consumers;

at the level of technology development - on the one hand, the development of artificial intelligence capable of generating attractive and plausible content on a large scale; on the other hand, the development of attention management technologies, including the use of sequential repetitive cycles (trigger, action and reward) to form stable habits that prevent out-of-the-box thinking.

Rumours, gossip, misinformation and disinformation

Rumours are the spread of unverified information. According to G.W. Allport's law, the main factors in the spread of rumours are the significance of the event and the uncertainty of the information.

One of the most formalised definitions of gossip is that of T. Dores Cruz, according to which gossip is a communication between people involving a sender, a receiver and a target who is absent from the communication or unaware of the content being communicated.

Gossip and rumours can mislead people regardless of whether the source of information made a mistake or actually intended to deceive.

This intention is often present when gossip is part of an intrigue, a plan of confrontation. In this case, we can speak of disinformation.

The reason for misleading the recipient of unverified information is rather the errors of the source of information than the presence of intent to deceive (Table 1). In this case, we can talk about misinformation.

There is currently no unified theory of misinformation and disinformation. Researchers [4, 5] have proposed a conceptual analysis of misinformation and disinformation, respectively. The purpose of conceptual analysis is to find a list of necessary and jointly sufficient conditions that correctly define this concept.

In particular, «you disinform X if and only if:

1. You disseminate information i.
2. You believe that p is false.
3. You foresee that X is likely to infer from the content of information i that p.
4. p is false.
5. It is reasonable for X to infer from the content of information i that p.» [5]

Table 1. Probable reasons for misleading the recipient of information by the source of information

	Misinformation	Disinformation
Rumours	The credibility of the source of disinformation Confidence of the misinformers Social influence	Attractiveness of the topic Needs of the recipient of the information
Gossip	Indifference to the truth of the recipient of information Wishful thinking by the recipient of information	Plausibility of misinformation Repetition of a message from different sources

Source: developed by the author.

At the same time, misleading the recipient of rumours and gossip can be caused by reasons that are more complex.

Quality of information derived from rumours and its value

According to L. Floridi [6], «the first major area of developing research is IQ in unstructured data, particularly on trust, provenance and reputation. The core idea is very simple: where do the data come from (provenance), are they any good (trust) and is their source any good (reputation)?»

D.Fallis suggests that «there are four important areas to consider when verifying the accuracy of information: (i) authority, (ii) independent corroboration, (iii) plausibility and support, and (iv) presentation» [7].

The author assessed the quality of information obtained on the basis of rumours, the level of information quality did not exceed 0.3 (with a maximum value of 1). The proposed method took into account such dimensions as source reputation, consistency, objectivity, accessibility, reliability, accuracy. The evaluation was conducted for the reputation loss objective. The objectivity evaluation considered the presence of conflict of interest as well as the proportion of facts in the report.

The value of information to the audience is not necessarily determined by its quality.

The following measurable factors can influence the value of information to the audience:

attractiveness;

plausibility;

usefulness.

In fact, these three factors are a distortion of Platonic triad (Truth, Goodness, and Beauty).

In this case, beauty is replaced by attractiveness, truth by plausibility, and goodness by a concrete tangible benefit at a given time for a particular subject.

The attention of the audience is drawn to «the effect of inside story», and «bad news --bad news about somebody, or bad news for somebody» [1].

Messages about what they already know about are attractive to audiences, «because for rational beings to see or recognize their experience in a new material form is an unbought grace of life» [1].

Thus, there are many opportunities to increase the audience's interest in the message, to increase its value.

Readers (audiences) in relation to rumours can make the following decisions:

to listen to the rumour or not;

to believe the rumours or not

to take rumours into account or not;

whether or not to spread the rumours..

The decision to listen to a rumour or not is influenced by curiosity, namely "two kinds of curiosity: self-interested - inspired by the hope of acquiring useful information, and self-loving - caused by the desire to know what is unknown to others" [8].

The quality of the information may not be high enough to believe it, but the interest in the topic may be sufficient to consider an unverified message.

The duration of attention paid to a message is not enough to measure its quality, but may be enough to decide to share it.

Attention deficit leads to a greater likelihood of choosing the peripheral path of information processing as not requiring cognitive effort [9].

Consequently, the situation of increased information value and decreased information quality under attention deficit creates the basis for increased communication risks as well as reputational risks because of misinformation.

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